

ISic1528

I.Sicily inscription 1528

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Catacomb of S.Giovanni

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 26701

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Ἐνθάδε κίτε Πολυχ
2. ρόνιος καὶ Σεραπία
3. Ἠγόρασεν τῷ τότε
4. ε καιρῷ Πολυχρονίου
5. αὶ Σεραπία ἐπὶ τῷ κυρί
6. ω μου ἐπισκόπῳ Συρα
7. κοσίῳ

Apparatus

Text after Agnello 1953

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645028

Bibliography

Agnello, S.L. 1953. Silloge di iscrizioni paleocristiane della Sicilia. Rome. At no.32
undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-
Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità*. At 36

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